

УДК 330(477)

*Sofia Likunova**Науковий керівник: канд. екон. наук, доц. Іванова О. А.*

RECOVERY OF UKRAINIAN ENTERPRISES IN CONDITIONS OF UNCERTAINTY

The article examines the process of adaptation and recovery of Ukrainian enterprises in conditions of military and economic uncertainty. The article is a relevant and meaningful analysis of the activities of Ukrainian entrepreneurship in the context of an unprecedented crisis.

The main challenges and threats that affect the economic sector in modern conditions are presented. The consequences they lead to are also indicated, both in general terms and with specific examples. In addition, the critical state of small business is described, which is confirmed by statistical indicators.

The main part of the article is an analysis of the most common strategies for overcoming uncertainty, including: business relocation, militarization of economic activity, reorganization and M&A, international market expansion, and innovative solutions. The author uses statistical data and examples of the activities of Ukrainian enterprises to balance theoretical data and applied material, which deepens the understanding of the object of research. An analysis of the effectiveness of strategies in the macroeconomic environment was carried out. Conclusions are drawn regarding the feasibility of the analyzed strategies in the short and long term. Special attention is focused on cross-cultural communication and interaction between Ukraine and the EU, and their impact on the business sector.

Overall, the transformation of entrepreneurship since the beginning of the full-scale invasion is analyzed. Critical factors and the level of adaptation of Ukrainian enterprises to them are presented.

Key words: Ukrainian enterprises, war risks, economic uncertainty, business adaptability, recovery strategies, militarization of the economy, relocation of enterprises, mergers and acquisitions (M&A), underground industrial park.

Лікунова Софія В'ячеславівна. Відновлення діяльності українських підприємств в умовах невизначеності.

У статті досліджено процес адаптації та відновлення українських підприємств в умовах воєнної та економічної невизначеності. Стаття є

актуальним і змістовним аналізом діяльності українського підприємництва в умовах безпрецедентної кризи.

Наведено основні виклики та загрози, які впливають на господарський сектор у сучасних умовах. Також зазначено наслідки до яких вони призводять, як узагальнено, так і з конкретними прикладами. Окрім цього описано критичний стан малого підприємництва, що підтверджено статистичними показниками.

Основна частина статті це аналіз найпоширеніших стратегій подолання невизначеності, серед яких: релокація бізнесу, мілітаризація господарської діяльності, реорганізація та M&A, експансія міжнародного ринку та інноваційні рішення. Автор використовує статистичні дані та приклади діяльності українських підприємств для балансу між теоретичними даними та прикладним матеріалом, що поглиблює розуміння об'єкта дослідження. Здійснено аналіз ефективності стратегій у макроекономічному середовищі. Зроблено висновки щодо доцільності проаналізованих стратегій в коротко-строковій і довгостроковій перспективах. Окрема увага зосереджена на крос-культурній комунікації та взаємодії Україна-ЄС, їхньому впливу на підприємницький сектор.

Загалом проаналізовано трансформацію підприємництва від початку повномасштабного вторгнення. Наведено критичні чинники та рівень адаптованості українських підприємств до них.

Ключові слова: українські підприємства, воєнні ризики, економічна невизначеність, адаптивність бізнесу, стратегії відновлення, мілітаризація господарства, релокація підприємств, злиття та поглинання (M&A), підземний індустріальний парк.

In times of uncertainty and the greatest challenges, the issue of preserving and potentially restoring the business sector remains acute. The Ukrainian economy is suffering losses that are already estimated at billions of hryvnias. Approximately 19% of the country's territory is under occupation, a hybrid war is ongoing, and there is a constant threat of shelling and worsening of the situation [1].

Ukrainian enterprises are forced to make quick adaptive decisions. Even in the first days of the full-scale invasion, the question of whether to continue or stop operations arose. There is still uncertainty about the sufficient prospects in the current conditions, as pressure increases.

The factors that cause the greatest burden are directly or indirectly related to the war. First of all, these are military risks with the threat of

physical destruction or damage to assets. They lead to an increase in the level of migration, which in turn can cause a decrease in consumer demand and a personnel crisis. It is also worth noting the logistical gaps and power supply disruptions that make it impossible for enterprises to operate. Pressure from the state administration is also increasing. Control and regulatory policy are being strengthened, mainly to combat tax evasion and fraud. The tax burden on enterprises is increasing, and the updating of social standards (such as the minimum wage) is pressing. As a result of the combination of these factors, for example, we can note the negative dynamics among Sole Traders in 2025. The number of closed Sole Traders outweighed the number of opened ones by approximately 46%. At the same time, the number of closures increased by 44% compared to 2024 (in which the dynamics were positive due to the predominance of opening Sole Traders) [2]. An important clarification is that small enterprises make up the majority of the total number of all enterprises in Ukraine (over 80%). Therefore, their sharp reduction significantly destabilizes the economy: it reduces the level of potential budget revenues, creates a shortage of goods and services, causes a shortage of jobs, reduces innovation, etc.

Despite constant pressure, Ukrainian enterprises demonstrate high adaptability to modern challenges. If at first there was a problem of “survival” of the business sector, now strategies for recovery and further development are increasingly being implemented. This is confirmed by the variety of approaches to continuing activities and its constant expansion. A relatively common solution was business relocation. For example, thanks to a program from the Ministry of Economy, enterprises from the most affected regions were relocated to less vulnerable ones. The most popular directions were: from the South to the Center and from the East to the Center. The main industries subject to the relocation program were: Wholesale and retail trade, Construction and the IT sector. The relocation trend itself turned out to be interesting. This means that a significant number of enterprises were not relocated abroad or to central/western territories, but were retained within their regions, located closer to regional centers. This had positive consequences, in particular, reducing the territorial imbalance in the distribution of enterprises between regions.

The trend among enterprises is not only relocation, but also a change in production profile. There is a certain militarization of the economic sector. That is, enterprises are re-profiling their activities for the needs of the armed forces. For example, enterprises in the light industry sector are focusing on the production of military clothing and footwear; enterprises in the food industry sector are creating long-term storage products, canned goods and dry rations; car services have begun to reorient themselves towards military equipment, etc. In the short term, such processes have a positive impact, as they allow enterprises to “survive” and meet demand. However, in long-term planning, negative consequences may arise, such as a shortage of civilian goods and services with subsequent economic imbalance.

Unique times favor non-standard solutions. Current features have given impetus to the development of individual industries and enterprises. Accordingly, effective reorganization has taken place. First of all, it is about mergers and acquisitions (in the context of Ukraine, the second process prevails). In 2024, the French NJJ Holding acquired Datagroup-Volya and Lifecell, combining them into a new large telecommunications platform [4]. In turn, in 2025, Kyivstar acquired 97% of the shares of the Uklon service (in fact, Kyivstar absorbed the online service through its parent company VEON) [5]. These strategic moves are aimed at expanding corporate capabilities and fostering innovation, as a result of the high quality of the strategy, we can note the growth of profit indicators after the merger/acquisition process.

There are enough examples of the rapid development of companies after the start of a full-scale invasion. In conditions of uncertainty, the understanding of partnership is being redefined. New, sometimes voluntary connections are emerging, such as the interaction between Monobank and Ukrgasbank. Thanks to the increased focus on European integration, opportunities for cross-cultural communication and entry into international markets are expanding. Ukrainian enterprises are increasingly entering the EU market. The target audience for well-known companies (Nova Post, Lviv Croissants, Bob Snail) at the initial stages is Ukrainian immigrants, until the network becomes a sufficient number of the local population. Nevertheless, war risks remain. Enterprises in front-line regions are the

most vulnerable compared to others. Earlier, we mentioned relocation programs that practically solve problems only in short-term planning. But there are different types of relocation, and entrepreneurs find very creative ways to preserve production capacities. A non-standard and at the same time quite effective solution to overcoming crisis conditions is moving underground. Thus, continuity of activity and security are ensured, as factors that initiate the expediency of entrepreneurial activity. Currently, these are small-scale underground spaces (of those that are known) that do not have sufficient capacity to organize the system. But the idea of underground construction is developing quite actively. For example, a study is being conducted on the idea of building the first underground industrial park in Ukraine in Kharkiv. Which has an ecosystem that ensures economic development using innovative methods. The implementation of such a project requires significant investments that can be collected only under co-financing conditions.

In fact, Ukrainian enterprises, even without implementing bold project decisions, often face financial difficulties. Therefore, the need for grants remains relevant. To ensure effective activity, state and international grant programs for development and support have been implemented. They apply not only to existing enterprises, but are also designed to develop the economic sector by creating new entities. This is a kind of incentive for the restoration and development of entrepreneurship in crisis conditions, which is designed to facilitate the adaptation process. Over the years of Russia's armed aggression against Ukraine, domestic enterprises have inevitably adapted, improving tools for continuing their activities. In the realities of the existing conditions, long-term planning in decisions made becomes almost impossible, giving way to short-term prospects as a risk. Nevertheless, this is still the most effective way to stabilize crisis phenomena. Ukrainian enterprises are restoring their activities to the indicators by 2022, but at the same time there are no clear strategies for systemic development in the continuation of future years due to uncertainty. Since pessimistic scenarios of events often occur, which require high-quality and deep crisis management.

Despite constant pressure, the economic sector has unique solutions that ensure not only local recovery, but also the expansion of international markets. In recent years, the connection between Ukraine and the European

part of the world has deepened, which gives enterprises greater prospects. Ukrainian companies are becoming recognizable and desirable, which ensures the creation of new communication links and the receipt of additional resources, which are urgently needed.

Today, most enterprises have passed the “survival” limit and achieved stable indicators under significant pressure. This indicates a high level of enterprise resilience, and for its maintenance and increase, increased internal and external support and encouragement.

Список бібліографічних посилань

1. Слово і Діло (2025). *Скільки території України окупувала росія* [online]. Available at: https://www.slovoidilo.ua/2025/12/17/infografika/suspilstvo/skilky-terytoriyi-ukrayiny-okupuvala-rosiya#google_vignette [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

2. Дія. Бізнес (2025). *Динаміка відкриття ФОП у 2025 році* [online]. Available at: <https://www.business.diia.gov.ua/news/dynamika-vidkryttia-fop-u-2025-rotsi> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

3. Інформаційне управління (2022). *Програма релокації бізнесу - дієвий інструмент створення надійного економічного тилу, - в цьому переконаний Голова Комітету з питань бюджету Юрій Арістов*. Офіційний вебпортал парламенту України [online]. Available at: <https://www.rada.gov.ua/news/razom/223016.html> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

4. Data group (2024). *Угоди з придбання NJJ Holding компаній Датагруп-Volia та lifecell завершено* [online]. Available at: <https://www.datagroup.ua/povnyu/ugodu-z-pridbannya-njj-holding-kompanij-datagrup-volia-ta-li-500> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

5. Тарасовський Ю. (2025). *«Київстар» купує Uklon за \$155 млн*. Forbes.ua [online]. Available at: <https://forbes.ua/news/kiiivstar-pridbav-uklon-za-155-mln-grn-19032025-28143> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

6. Kharkiv IT Cluster (2025). *Підсумки хакатону Underground Tech: що створили команди?* [online]. Available at: <https://it-kharkiv.com/news/ua/pidsumky-khakatonu-underground-tech> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

References

1. Slovo i Dilo (2025). *Skilky terytoriyi Ukrayiny okupuvala rosiya* [online]. Available at: https://www.slovoidilo.ua/2025/12/17/infografika/suspilstvo/skilky-terytoriyi-ukrayiny-okupuvala-rosiya#google_vignette [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

2. Diia. Biznes (2025). *Dynamika vidkryttia FOP u 2025 rotsi* [online]. Available

at: <https://www.business.diiia.gov.ua/news/dynamika-vidkryttia-fop-u-2025-rotsi> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

3. Informatsiine upravlinnia (2022). *Prohrama relokatsii biznesu - diievyyi instrument stvorennia nadiinoho ekonomichnoho tylu, - v tsomu perekonanyi Holova Komitetu z pytan biudzhetu Yurii Aristov*. Ofitsiinyi vebportal parlamentu Ukrainy [online]. Available at: <https://www.rada.gov.ua/news/razom/223016.html> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

4. Data group (2024). *Uhodu z prydbannia NJJ Holding kompanii Datahrup-Volia ta Lifecell zaversheno* [online]. Available at: <https://www.datagroup.ua/novyny/ugodu-z-pridbannya-njj-holding-kompanij-datagrup-volia-ta-li-500> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

5. Tarasovskiy Yu. (2025). «Kyivstar» kupuie Uklon za \$155 mln. Forbes.ua [online]. Available at: <https://forbes.ua/news/kiiivstar-pridbav-uklon-za-155-mln-grn-19032025-28143> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].

6. Kharkiv IT Cluster (2025). *Pidsumky khakatonu Underground Tech: shcho stvoryly komandy?* [online]. Available at: <https://it-kharkiv.com/news/ua/pidsumky-khakatonu-underground-tech> [Accessed 1 Mar. 2026].